

POLYBENZIMIDAZOLE COMPOSITES

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Summary

A number of aerospace structures currently under development will be manufactured from materials capable of withstanding short time temperature exposures of 1200°F-1400°F. In addition to metals, metal alloys, and metal matrix composites, high temperature resistant polymeric composite materials are being developed for these applications. The traditional justification for the use of structural composites, i.e., superior specific strengths and stiffnesses have spurred the development of polybenzimidazole (PBI) composites for use in short term high temperature applications. The purpose of this paper is to provide the reader with an introduction to the history, chemistry, processing, and typical mechanical properties of polybenzimidazole composites. In addition, the effects of porosity on the mechanical properties of composites will be discussed.

History and Chemistry of PBI

Polybenzimidazole is a general name for polymers that contain the thermally stable benzimidazole ring system in their backbone. Aliphatic polybenzimidazoles were first described in a U.S. patent in 1959 (Reference 1). The first fully aromatic polybenzimidazoles were reported two years later (Reference 2) by Vogel and Marvel and were synthesized by the condensation polymerization of an aromatic tetraamine with an aromatic dicarboxylic acid or derivative thereof. Because the fully aromatic polybenzimidazoles possess better thermal stability than the aliphatic polybenzimidazoles, further development efforts have been concentrated on the fully aromatic polymers.

The polybenzimidazole that has been developed to the greatest extent is poly-2,2'-(*m*-phenylene)-5,5'-bibenzimidazole. This material is synthesized from 3,3'-diaminobenzidine and diphenylisophthalate.

The overall reaction scheme is shown in Figure 1. An examination of this chemical reaction reveals that two moles of phenol and two moles of water are evolved for every mole of polymer formed. This amount of volatile evolution represents significant mass loss and causes problems with processing the polymer. Some solutions to polymer processing will be discussed later.

Figure 1 Polybenzimidazole

One key to processing PBI is an understanding of the polymerization mechanism. At first glance one would suspect that the amine groups on the tetraamine would react with the ether groups to form an aminoamide. The aminoamide would then dehydrate to form the benzimidazole ring. This mechanism would imply that phenol is evolved first and water is evolved last in the polymerization process.

In 1964, Wrasidlo and Levine (Reference 3) performed a very comprehensive study of the PBI polymerization mechanism. The results of their study is depicted in Figures 2 and 3. The conclusions they draw are exactly opposite to what one would first suspect as a reasonable reaction mechanism for polybenzimidazole polymer formation. The kinetic data they developed indicated that the tetraamine is rapidly consumed to form an aldol type intermediate which evolves water to form a Schiff's base. The Schiff's base then evolves phenol to form the final polymer structure. As a result, phenol evolution is the rate determining step of the polymerization reaction. Kinetic data developed as MDAC-St. Louis tends to support the kinetic data generated by Wrasidlo and Levine.

Polybenzimidazole is a linear polymer that can exhibit thermoplastic behavior at very high temperatures. The linear nature of the polymer can be explained by the Wrasidlo-Levine mechanistic data. The postulated Schiff's base can possess stereoisomerism. As a result, intramolecular hydrogen bonding can occur in the syn isomer but not in the anti isomer. The intramolecular hydrogen bonding forces the phenol elimination to be intramolecular rather than intermolecular. Intermolecular elimination would lead to branching and/or crosslinking whereas intramolecular elimination affords a nearly linear polymer.

Figure 2 Condensation mechanism for PBI

STEP 3: RING CLOSURE/PHENOL EVOLUTION

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Figure 3 Condensation mechanism for PBI

It should be pointed out that the thermoplastic behavior of polybenzimidazole can be eliminated, if necessary, for real world structural applications. Korshak and co-workers have proposed that at a high enough temperature, polybenzimidazole can form a crosslinked structure (Reference 4). These workers proposed that the polybenzimidazole can form nitrogen-nitrogen crosslinks in the polymer. This reaction is postulated to proceed via the labile N-H groups on the benzimidazole ring rather than through the hydrogens attached to the phenyl groups present in the polymer backbone. Work performed by Gillham also tends to support the conclusion that polybenzimidazole can be crosslinked (Reference 5).

Although other studies concerning the polymerization mechanism have appeared in the literature (References 6 and 7), Wrasidlo and Levine's work was done in the solid state. This more nearly reflects the actual state of affairs present in a composite material.

As was alluded to earlier in this section, the fact that water evolves first in the polymerization and phenol evolves later in the polymerization profoundly affects the processing of PBI. This will be discussed later in the section on processing.

Processing of PBI Composites

A number of techniques exist to process polybenzimidazole composites. These include autoclave processing, compression molding, press curing, and filament winding. However, regardless of the techniques, the important variables of time, temperature, and pressure control the final quality of the composite material.

Prior to 1982 typical PBI composites processed with autoclave technology possessed rather high void contents on the order of 8 to 15 percent. However, advances in processing technology since 1982 have resulted in the production of very low void content (< 3%) PBI composites using MDAC-St. Louis propriety processing techniques for press curing and compression molding as well as autoclave processing techniques (Reference 6).

Figure 4 presents a possible, though not optimum press cure cycle for PBI composites. As can be seen from an examination of the cure cycle, three distinct plateaus exist. These three plateaus (or holds) in the cure cycle exist for three distinct reasons. The first hold in the cycle is needed for resin flow, fiber wetting and compaction of the laminate. The second hold represents the bulk of the polymerization reaction. The third hold is present for crosslinking purposes and allows residual volatiles to diffuse from the laminate. Depending on part size and geometry, a free standing post cure may be necessary to develop the final desired mechanical properties.

An examination for the cure cycle presented also shows that different pressures are applied to the laminate at specific points in the cure cycle. As was mentioned previously, water is evolved first in the reaction and phenol last. The different pressures are needed to keep the volatile by products in an appropriate physical state in order to facilitate their removal from the composite. Extremely low void content laminates (< 1-3%) of carbon/PBI have been manufactured using the press cure process at MDAC-St. Louis.

Figure 4 Typical PBI cure cycle

The autoclave processing detailed in Delano's paper (Reference 8) differs significantly from the press cure process in that much lower pressures are used to produce high quality composites. Both Nextel/PBI and S2 Glass/PBI composites containing less than 3% void content have been produced by this method. Work performed by Khubander et. al. (see Reference 8) on the autoclave processing of PBI composites have also yielded low void content laminates.

Polybenzimidazole may also be compression molded into low void content composites. However, because of the processing technique, a much higher molecular weight polymer must be used for compression molding as compared to laminate fabrication. The early work done on compression molding polybenzimidazole was reported by Levine and Stacy (Reference 9). The particular polybenzimidazole used in this work is the same one used today except that it was prepared by reacting 3,3'-diaminobenzidine with isophthalamide. In this reaction ammonia and water are the volatile by-products of the polymerization reaction. Data on the compressive strength of pure molded resin is shown in Figure 5 as a function of temperature. As can be seen from an examination of this data, neat PBI molded specimens made from the isophthalamide synthesized polymer retain nearly 70% of their room temperature mechanical properties after 10 minutes exposure to 800°F.

Recent work performed by MDAC-St. Louis has concentrated on a high molecular weight version of the poly (2,2'-*m*-phenylene-5,5'-benzimidazole) polymer. This particular polymer, available from Celanese Corp., is also compression moldable. The material is synthesized from the same monomers used to make the Acurex Corp. low molecular weight prepreg material: 3,3'-diaminobenzidine and diphenylisophthalate. Although the process has not yet been optimized, tensile strengths of nearly 10,000 psi have been obtained from compression molding this polymer.

TEMPERATURE (°F)	YIELD STRENGTH (KSI)	ULTIMATE STRENGTH (KSI)
72	54	—
201	46	—
395	29	59.0
600	14	58.0
700	8	54.0
800	2	40.4
1000	0.2	0.7

NOTE: SPECIMENS EXPOSED 10 MINUTES TO TEMPERATURE PRIOR TO TEST

Figure 5 Compressive strength of molded PBI resin (No reinforcement)

Porosity Effects on the Mechanical Properties of PBI Composites

Researchers have shown that porosity (void content) adversely affects the mechanical properties of composites. For example, Bohlmann has shown that for carbon/epoxy composites made from unidirectional AS4/3501-6 material a 2% porosity decreases room temperature interlaminar shear strength by 31% (Reference 10). For unidirectional carbon/PMR-15 laminates, Holmes has shown that room temperature interlaminar shear strengths are reduced from 12% to 22% for porosities of 4%-9% (Reference 11). In both examples, these reductions are related to reference composites containing nearly zero porosity. Data concerning strength reduction as a function of porosity in polybenzimidazole composites is not nearly as well developed as for the materials mentioned in the previous two examples. Preliminary data developed at MDAC-St. Louis indicate that some level of porosity will be tolerable for carbon/polybenzimidazole composites, and that this level of porosity is larger than the tolerable level of porosity for carbon/epoxy systems. However, further precisely controlled analytical studies will be needed to conclusively confirm or deny this observation.

The material effects presented in these two examples are not the only variables that affect the determination of tolerable void contents. Fibers of varying diameter, for example, need to be supported by the matrix to various degrees to achieve efficient compressive strengths. In addition, woven fibers and unidirectional fibers present in a given matrix will react differently, to a degree, for a given level of porosity. One other important consideration (and variable) is both the size and the distribution of the porosity in the composite material.

The information presented here should not prevent any materials researcher from attempting to achieve the most desirable goal possible: the processing of a given composite material with no measurable level of porosity. It does serve to support the argument that new material systems should not be regarded as inadequate or unworkable without a thorough and comprehensive investigation into the effects of porosity (and other material defects) on the appropriate mechanical properties of a given composite material system for a range of temperatures over which a particular structure is required to function.

Typical Mechanical Properties of Carbon/PBI Composites

Figure 6 presents some typical values of both tensile and flexural strengths for carbon/PBI composites as a function of temperature. This data indicates that the percentage retention of room temperature flexural strength at 800°F and 1200°F is 63% and 18% for three minutes exposure to these temperatures when tested at temperature. In terms of organic matrix composites, the percentage strength retention at 1200°F is excellent.

Figure 7 presents both flexural and tensile modulus as a function of temperature for the carbon/PBI composite material. In terms of stiffness retention at 800°F and 1200°F, the PBI composite material retains 63% and 37% of its room temperature stiffness, at these temperatures, respectively. These values represent excellent retention of properties which reflect a material that is adequate for 1200°F service environments.

Figure 8 presents interlaminar shear data for carbon/PBI laminates as a function of temperature. At 900°F, approximately 60% of the room temperature shear strength is retained whereas at 1200°F approximately 26% of the room temperature shear strength is retained. This data shows the rather remarkable thermal stability of the polybenzimidazole polymer matrix. Similar testing on polyimides, for example, has shown that at 1200°F, essentially no shear strength would be detectable in a similar composite.

Figure 6 Mechanical properties vs. temperature (U)

PBI RESIN/ T-300 GRAPHITE

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Figure 7 Elastic modulus properties vs. temperature

Figure 8 Short beam shear strength of PBI unidirectional and quasi-isotropic laminate

Conclusions:

Recently, breakthroughs in polybenzimidazole processing have resulted in the production of high quality, low porosity polybenzimidazole composites. As a result, these materials are attractive and viable candidates for structural application at 1200-1400°F. A significant amount of effort still remains in terms of optimizing lowest cost manufacturing processes, establishing tolerable defect levels for a given application, and developing an appropriate design data base for these types of composite materials.

References

1. K. C. Brinker and I. V. Robinson, US Pat No 2,895,948 (1959).
2. H. Vogel and C. S. Marvel, J. Polymer. Sci., vol. 50, 511 (1961).
3. W. Wrasidlo and H. Levine, J. Polymer Sci., A, vol. 2, 4795 (1964).
4. U. U. Korshak et. al., Uysokomolekul. Soedin., vol. 8, 7797 (1966).
5. J. K. Gillham, Science, vol. 139, 494 (1963).
6. D. N. Gray et. al., J. Macromol. Sci., (Chem), A-1, 395 (1967).
7. A. A. Izyneev et. al., Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR Ser. Khim., 1828, (1963).
8. C. B. Delano, High Temple Workshop V, Monterey, CA., 1985.
9. H. Levine and R. D. Stacy, AFML-TR-65-350, (1966).
10. R. E. Bohlmann et. al., MDC Report A7361, 1981.
11. G. A. Holmes, High Temple Workshop V, Monterey, CA 1985.

